

WEBO

Circular wooden windows with low maintenance

Wooden window frames, facade elements, BIM design or unique wood solutions. WEBO focuses on circular design, integration of recycled materials and modularity for easy replacements

Highlights of innovative features

- The outside window parts are made of chemically modified wood that allows for very low maintenance.
- The modularity of the window frame allows for exchanging only parts of the window if necessary.
- The interior part of the window frame is made of recycled or sustainably sourced wood.

Modular window frames allow for combining high performance modified wood on the outside and well insulating wood for the inner parts of the frame

Company | Ownership of innovation

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